

Supplementary material

Transient effects of snow cover duration on primary growth and leaf traits in a tundra shrub

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Supplementary Figure 1: Mean air temperature (°C), soil water content (%) over the days of the year (doy) and over months considering the period 2018-2020, registered at Giau Pass (A) and snow height (cm) recorded at the Falzarego Pass weather station in the period 2018-2020 and in average for the 1988-2020 period (B). Data are interpolated through spline function. Dashed lines represent the doy on which snow was completely melted.

Supplementary Figure 2: Elongation trend of 2018, 2019, 2020 of *Juniperus communis* L. shoots over day of the year (doy) for the control (green), uncovered (orange) treatment and covered treatment (blue). Solid line is the elongation trend modelled by GAM model, coloured band around solid line represents the confidence interval at 95% of probability.

Supplementary Figure 3: Outcome of linear mixed-effects models (nested ANOVA) of leaf traits. Mean \pm SE stomatal density (A; n°/mm^2), needle area (B; mm^2) and dry weight per leaf (C; mg) of early-melt (orange), control (green) and late-melt (blue) shrubs in 2018, 2019 and 2020. Equal letters indicate that there are no significant differences between groups ($p > 0.05$).

Supplementary Figure 4: Outcome of linear mixed-effects models (nested ANOVA) of specific leaf area. Mean \pm SE specific leaf area (mm^2/mg) of uncovered (orange), control (green) and covered (blue) shrubs, in 2018, 2019, 2020 and in average from 2018 to 2020 (mean).

Supplementary Figure 5: Outcome of linear mixed-effects models (nested ANOVA) of leaf NSC content. Mean \pm SE starch (g/g) and soluble sugars (g/g) leaf content of early-melt (E; orange), control (C; green) and late-melt (L; blue) shrubs, in 2018, 2019, 2020 measured at the beginning (June) and at the end (September) of the growing season.

year	E-C	L-C	E-L
2018	53	35	88
2019	95	37	132
2020	39	27	66
mean	62	33	95

Supplementary Table 1: Difference of days of snow removal for early snowmelt (E), control (C) and late snowmelt (L) treatments in 2018, 2019, 2020 and in average for these three years (mean).

Max length (mm)	SE (mm)	treatment	year
20.31	2.38	C	2018
31.86	2.96	L	
32.77	6.71	E	
19.21	2.41	C	2019
17.43	2.40	L	
24.29	4.48	E	
21.47	1.82	C	2020
21.38	1.49	L	
22.48	2.39	E	
21.02	2.33	C	mean
20.55	2.07	L	
22.80	3.25	E	

Supplementary Table 2: Maximum length (mm) reached and SE of primary shoots of *Juniperus communis* growing at Giau pass, measured in 2018, 2019, 2020 and in average for these three years (mean), under early snowmelt (E), control (C) and late snowmelt (L) treatments.

Max slope	treatment	year	day
0.38	C	2018	179
0.44	L		223
0.45	E		185
0.65	C	2019	177
0.51	L		201
0.70	E		177
0.50	C	2020	184
0.49	L		193
0.47	E		185
0.54	C	mean	182
0.50	L		196
0.55	E		183

Supplementary Table 3: Maximal slope of the elongation curve modelled by GAM model of *Juniperus communis* growing at Giau pass, measured in 2018, 2019, 2020 and in average for these three years (mean), under early snowmelt (E), control (C) and late snowmelt (L) treatments.

	year	treatment	mean	SE	n
STOMATAL DENSITY	2018	E	268	6	25
		C	260	6	25
		L	254	6	25
	2019	E	266	6	25
		C	260	6	25
		L	254	6	25
	2020	E	266	6	24
		C	262	8	18
		L	254	4	25
	tot	E	260	2	114
		C	254	4	110
		L	254	2	120
LEAF AREA	2018	E	8.59	0.2	154
		C	8.01	0.22	151
		L	9.15	0.23	129
	2019	E	9.1	0.17	168
		C	8.89	0.17	143
		L	9.77	0.18	143
	2020	E	8.97	0.17	159
		C	8.9	0.14	157
		L	9.45	0.2	141
	tot	E	9.19	0.085	682
		C	8.8	0.086	661
		L	9.78	0.093	635
DRY WEIGHT	2018	E	2.23	2.83	153
		C	1.76	1.32	151
		L	2.32	2.30	131
	2019	E	2.15	1.90	169
		C	2.14	1.10	141
		L	2.25	8.73	143
	2020	E	2.08	1.12	154
		C	1.97	1.28	157
		L	2.17	2.74	150
	mean	E	2.15	1.12	476
		C	1.97	7.79	449
		L	2.25	1.15	424

Supplementary Table 4: Mean and SE of stomatal density (n°/mm^2), area per leaf (mm^2) and dry weight per leaf (mg) of *Juniperus communis* growing at Giau pass, measured in 2018, 2019, 2020 and in average for these three years (mean), under early snowmelt (E), control (C) and late snowmelt (L) treatments. N is sample depth.

	year	month	treatment	mean	SE	n
STARCH	2018	jun	E	0.091	0.012	5
			C	0.108	0.009	5
			L	0.019	0.004	5
		set	E	0.007	0.000	5
			C	0.008	0.001	5
			L	0.009	0.001	5
	2019	jun	E	0.081	0.008	5
			C	0.080	0.006	5
			L	0.006	0.003	5
		set	E	0.014	0.003	5
			C	0.009	0.002	5
			L	0.020	0.005	5
	2020	jun	E	0.073	0.003	5
			C	0.071	0.003	5
			L	0.022	0.008	5
		set	E	0.017	0.005	5
			C	0.014	0.003	5
			L	0.028	0.006	5
	mean	jun	E	0.08	0.005	15
			C	0.08	0.003	15
			L	0.02	0.003	15
set		E	0.01	0.002	15	
		C	0.01	0.001	15	
		L	0.02	0.004	15	

Supplementary Table 5: Mean and SE of starch leaf content (g/g) of *Juniperus communis* growing at Giau pass, measured in 2018, 2019, 2020 and in average for these three years (mean in June and September), under early snowmelt (E), control (C) and late snowmelt (L) treatments. *n* is sample depth.

	year	month	treatment	mean	SE	n
SOLUBLE SUGARS	2018	jun	E	0.225	0.020	5
			C	0.214	0.013	5
			L	0.250	0.010	5
		set	E	0.232	0.016	5
			C	0.208	0.007	5
			L	0.196	0.017	5
	2019	jun	E	0.248	0.025	5
			C	0.294	0.011	5
			L	0.248	0.017	5
		set	E	0.280	0.023	5
			C	0.187	0.009	5
			L	0.310	0.035	5
	2020	jun	E	0.239	0.028	5
			C	0.301	0.009	5
			L	0.331	0.012	5
		set	E	0.274	0.017	5
			C	0.368	0.020	5
			L	0.388	0.011	5
	mean	jun	E	0.24	0.017	15
			C	0.27	0.012	15
			L	0.28	0.013	15
set		E	0.26	0.012	15	
		C	0.25	0.033	15	
		L	0.30	0.025	15	

Supplementary Table 6: Mean and SE of soluble sugar leaf content (g/g) of *Juniperus communis* growing at Giau pass, measured in 2018, 2019, 2020 and in average for these three years (mean in June and September), under early snowmelt (E), control (C) and late snowmelt (L) treatments. n is sample depth.